

Principal Leadership Style and Instructional Supervision as Determinants of Teachers' Job Commitment in Public Secondary Schools, Oyo State

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Abstract

Job commitment of teachers is very paramount in the realization of schools goals and objectives. With the awareness of the relevance of job commitment, numbers of researcher have carried out study exploring various variables that could bring about improvement of teachers job commitment in school. Thus, this paper examined principal leadership style and instructional supervision as determinants of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state. Survey design of correlational type was adopted. The population comprised 14,508 public secondary school teachers in Oyo State. 378 out of 14,508 teachers were selected using multistage sampling technique. Principal Leadership Style Questionnaire (PLSQ), Instructional Supervision Questionnaire (ISQ), and Teachers' Commitment Questionnaire (TCQ) were used to obtain the data for this study. Using Cronbach's Alpha measure of internal consistency, a reliability coefficient of 0.843, 0.751 and 0.651 were generated for (PLSQ), (ISQ) and respectively which showed that the questionnaires were reliable. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions raised while multiple regression statistics was used to test hypotheses. The result of the study revealed that the level of job commitment with average mean score of 3.07 to be moderate and there is significant relationship among principal leadership style, instructional supervision and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state, Nigeria among other findings. Based on the findings, it was recommended that the principal should improve their efficacy of their instructional leadership through provision of feedback to teachers at the end of learning observation and sustain their effort in checking their teachers' scheme of work every term.

Keywords: Leadership styles, instructional supervision, job commitment and secondary schools.

Introduction

Structured in different levels, formal education plays a crucial role in achieving the desired national development. Each level is designed to meet specific goals and objectives that, when accomplished, contribute to the overall educational objectives. By successfully accomplishing these objectives, the nation can ultimately attain the desired level of development. Regarding post-basic education, there are two key objectives: equipping students for the workforce and preparing them for further education. Perceiving the achievement of these aims necessitates certain perspectives, such as evaluating graduates' character alongside their academic accomplishments. Researchers primarily use academic performance as an indicator to assess the achievement of goals and objectives in secondary schools. This is often done through standardized tests such as WAEC and NECO. The academic performance of students in secondary schools depends on several factors, including but not limited to the level of commitment exhibited by teachers in the school.

The commitment of teachers refers to their determination to remain in the teaching profession or a specific school regardless of any challenges they may face. It represents the level of loyalty teachers have towards the teaching profession or the institution of the school. Onukwu, Tiebebedigha, and Okojie (2020) defined teachers' job commitment as the active engagement and contribution of teachers in the school's activities, aiming to achieve set objectives. It involves the teachers' awareness of utilizing their capabilities, expertise, and even resources to their fullest extent in order to reach organizational goals. It is the willingness of teachers to work towards the academic accomplishment of the students. According to Thien, Razak, and Ramayah (2014), teachers' commitment to their students' academic success can be observed from different perspectives, such as their commitment to the school, students, profession, and the act of teaching.

The idea of teacher commitment to students can be understood as teachers' active participation and accountability in the process of student learning. This includes teachers' willingness to support students who are experiencing personal difficulties, as well as their attentiveness and understanding of student growth and academic progress. Somech and Bogler (2002) stated that teacher commitment to profession means having an emotional connection to the job and a sense of personal fulfillment and identification as a teacher. Teacher commitment to profession is important because it enables the teachers to develop the needed skills and relationships to have a successful career regardless of the

school within which he or she is employed. Commitment to school involves teachers' understanding and embracing the school's goals and values, their dedication to working towards these objectives, and their eagerness to maintain their affiliation with the school. In the definition provided by Mowday, Porter, and Steers (1982), teachers displaying a high level of commitment to their school were anticipated to actively partake in actions that supported the school in accomplishing its objectives. Additionally, these teachers were expected to put in substantial effort that went beyond what was expected of them and continue their employment at the school.

Leadership and its various styles are highly significant within an organization like a school, as they have a profound impact on numerous facets of the institution, including instructional methods, academic progress, student behavior, teacher morale, and the overall environment of the school (Franklin, 2016). Hence, by selecting an appropriate leadership style, job satisfaction, commitment, and productivity among employees can be improved through motivation. The decision-making involvement and active participation of teachers rely on the leadership styles embraced by school principals. The probability of a teacher being dedicated to their job is significantly increased if they feel acknowledged and included in the decision-making process of their school. This is because it provides them with a strong sense of belonging. Therefore, the manner in which a school principal organizes and leads school activities could have an impact on the level of commitment demonstrated by the staff in that school. Supervision of instruction is a component of institutional factors that involves school principals and other relevant authorities working together or individually to enhance teaching and student activities. This is accomplished through overseeing and providing guidance to teachers during the instructional delivery process. Instructional supervision involves offering professional support and guidance to teachers and students with the aim of promoting effective teaching and learning in schools. Uwe and Godwin (2019) described instructional supervision as a means of enhancing all aspects and circumstances related to teaching and learning in order to facilitate improved learning outcomes. This entails providing the necessary leadership to encourage teachers to enhance their work and promote overall improvement in the teaching process.

Teachers in Oyo state appears not to be too committed to their job and this can be justify from their low level of punctuality; unwillingness to make efforts in the improvisation of unavailable instructional resources; as well as the relentless efforts seen in teachers in looking for opportunities

outside the profession. The low level of teachers' commitment in the state is well supported in the conclusion from the study carried out by Yusuf and Senimetu (2022) on principals' decision-making as predictors of job commitment among teachers in public secondary schools in Oyo state, Nigeria where it was found out that teachers' commitment in Oyo state was relatively low. This was further confirmed by the findings of the study of Oredein and Ebo (2021) which revealed the level of job commitment of public secondary school teachers in Oyo state to be low. This situation may be attributed to teachers' average working condition in the state. A number of teachers have observed that their psychological satisfaction is heightened by including them in the decision-making process at school, and that offering assistance when they encounter challenges during instructional activities is a great source of motivation for them. This makes one wonder if principal leadership style and instructional supervision can be a contributory factor towards teachers' level of commitment. Thus, the study examined principal leadership style and instructional supervision as determinants of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state.

The importance of teachers' dedication in the achievement of educational goals and objectives cannot be overstated. Only when teachers are committed will they be willing to wholeheartedly give their best in fulfilling their responsibilities. However, this is not the case in Oyo state as it is observed through visits to some secondary schools that the teachers' level of commitment seems to be quite low as seen in their subpar performance in the area of punctuality, preparation of lesson plan, zeal to carry the students along during instruction among others. The above researchers' observation is well supported by the empirical findings of the study conducted by Yusuf and Senimetu (2022) on principals' decision-making as predictors of job commitment among teachers in public secondary schools in Oyo state, Nigeria which found the level of teachers' commitment in Oyo state to be low. This low level of teachers' commitment is a very bad signal to students' academic achievement and the attainment of overall educational objectives. In order to discontinue this trend of low commitment among the teachers in Oyo State public secondary schools, measures need to be taken in order to ensure improvement in the level of teachers' commitment. Researchers as well as other educational stakeholders over the years have advanced various factors that could bring about improvement in teachers commitment, and by and large, job commitment could be a function of instructional supervision and leadership style of the school principals.

Many studies have been carried out that are related to this study; however, most of the works in one way or the other are different from this work. Some of these works include the study carried out by Yusuf and Senimetu (2022) on principal decision making as a predictor of job commitment among teachers in public secondary schools in Oyo state Nigeria. This study looks at principal decision making as factor of teachers' commitment while this study examined principal leadership style and instructional leadership. Another study was carried out by Oredein and Ebo (2021) on job and organizational commitment of public secondary schools teachers in Oyo State, Nigeria. The independent variables as well as the research methods adopted for the study are different from this study. Also, Amajuoyi (2022) carried out a study on principals' instructional supervision for improving the academic performance of students in secondary schools in Orumba South LGA. The study correlates principals' instructional with students' academic performance while this study examined teachers' commitment. From the numbers of literature reviewed, it has been observed that numbers of gaps have been left by the previous researchers in terms of variables and locale covered and these gaps are what the researcher intends to fill. Hence, the study examined principal leadership style and instructional supervision as determinants of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state.

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to examine principal leadership style and instructional supervision as determinants of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state.

Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. find out the level of teacher' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state;
2. determine the relationship between principals' leadership style and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state;
3. ascertain the relationship between instructional supervision and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state;

Research Question

1. What is the level of teacher' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state?

Research Hypotheses

H₀: Principal leadership style and instructional supervision are not predictors of teachers' commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between principals' leadership style and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between instructional supervision and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state.

Methodology

Descriptive survey design of correlational type was adopted to carry out the study. The target population of the study comprised all the 14,508 public secondary school teachers across the 33 local governments in Oyo state, Nigeria. 378 out of 14508 teachers were selected for the study. The sample size is obtained using Research Advisors (2007). Multistage sampling technique was used to select the respondents of the study. In the first stage, stratified random sampling technique was used to sample teachers proportionally across the 33 local governments in the state while simple random sampling technique was used in the second stage to select teachers within each local government. Stratified random sampling technique ensured there is equal representation of the teachers across the local governments while simple random sampling technique gave equal chance to the teachers within each local government. Self-designed questionnaires titled Principal Leadership Style Questionnaire (PLSQ); Instructional Supervision Questionnaire (ISQ); and an adapted Teachers' Commitment Questionnaire (TCQ) developed by Thien, Razak and Ramayah (2014) were used to obtain the data for the purpose of this study. The self-designed questionnaires were given to experts in the Department of Educational Management, University of Ilorin to check for the face and content validity. The recommendations were well incorporated. The results were further subjected to Scale Content Validity Index (SCV-I) and coefficients of .98, .88 and .92 were generated for PLSQ, ISQ and TCQ respectively which showed that the questionnaires are valid for the purpose they were designed. The reliability of the questionnaires were tested using Cronbach's Alpha measure of internal consistency and a reliability coefficient of 0.843, 0.751 and 0.651 were generated for Principal Leadership Style Questionnaire (PLSQ), Instructional Supervision Questionnaire (ISQ) and

Teachers' Commitment Questionnaire respectively. This indicated that the questionnaires were reliable for the purpose of this study. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions raised while inferential statistics of multiple regression statistics was used to test the formulated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

The researchers administered 378 questionnaires; however, 328 were retrieved indicating 86.77% recovery rate. Also, in the process of data screening, 5 responses were deleted due to report of significant outliers giving a total of 323 available for analysis purposes.

Research Question 1: What is the level of teacher' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state?

Table 1: Teachers' job commitment

SN	Variables	N	Mean	Std. D	Decision
1.	Commitment to School	323	3.1004	.53530	Moderate
2.	Commitment to Student	323	3.1831	.51215	Moderate
3.	Commitment to Profession	323	2.9249	.49030	Moderate
4.	Average		3.0695		Moderate

Key: Very Low 1.00-1.75; Low 1.76-2.50 Moderate 2.51-3.25; High 3.26-4.00

Table 1 revealed the level of job commitment with average mean score of 3.07 to be moderate in public secondary schools, Oyo State, Nigeria. The analysis further revealed that teachers are more committed to their students compare to what they have for the school and the teaching profession. The teachers are also high on their level of commitment to school compare to what was the situation in their commitment to profession.

H₀: Principal leadership style and instructional supervision are not predictors of teachers' commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state.

Table 2: Model Summary^b

Model	R	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.491 ^a	.241	.30583

a. Predictors: (Constant), Leadership Style, Instructional Supervision

b. Dependent Variable: Job Commitment

Table 3: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	9.489	2	4.745	50.727	.000 ^b
	Residual	29.930	320	.094		
	Total	39.419	322			

a. Dependent Variable: Job Commitment

b. Predictors: (Constant), Leadership Style, Instructional Supervision

Table 4: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		T	Sig.	Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
1 (Constant)	1.838	.125			14.724	.000	
Instructional Supervision	.150	.033	.257		4.562	.000	Rejected
Leadership Styles	.254	.047	.308		5.460	.000	Rejected

a. Dependent Variable: Job Commitment

The result on Table 3 showed a significant F-value (50.727) at 0.05 level of significance (0.000<0.05). This showed that the null hypothesis stated that principal leadership style and instructional supervision are not predictors of teachers' commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state was rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship among principal leadership style, instructional supervision teachers' commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state, Nigeria.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between principals' leadership style and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state.

Table 4a: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		T	Sig.	Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
1 (Constant)	1.838	.125			14.724	.000	
Leadership Styles	.254	.047	.308		5.460	.000	Rejected

a. Dependent Variable: Job Commitment

The result on Table 4a showed a significant t-value (5.460) and B (.254) at 0.05 level of significance ($0.000 < 0.05$). This revealed that the stated null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between principals' leadership style and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state is rejected. Thus, there is significant positive relationship between principals' leadership style and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between instructional supervision and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state.

Table 4b: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		T	Sig.	Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
1 (Constant)	1.838	.125			14.724	.000	
Instructional Supervision	.150	.033	.257		4.562	.000	Rejected

a. Dependent Variable: Job Commitment

The result on Table 4b showed a significant t-value (4.562) and B (.150) at 0.05 level of significance ($0.000 < 0.05$). This revealed that the stated null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between instructional supervision and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state is rejected. Thus, there is significant positive correlation between instructional supervision and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Table 1 revealed the level of job commitment with average mean score of 3.07 to be moderate in public secondary schools, Oyo State, Nigeria. The analysis further revealed that teachers are more committed to their students compare to what they have for the school and the teaching profession. The teachers are also high on their level of commitment to school compare to what was the situation in their commitment to profession. This implies that teachers averagely don't enjoy teaching and if they could get a job different from being a teacher and paying the same amount, they would take it. However, the result showed that teachers believe their values and their school's values are very similar, they believe all students can succeed and it is their mission to ensure their success as well as

ensure good social relations among my students. The findings of the study disagree with the result of Oredein and Ebo (2021) which revealed the level of job commitment of public secondary school teachers was low. The result of the study also disagrees with that of Yusuf and Senimetu (2022) that showed the level of teachers' job commitment to be low. The disparity in the findings of the study may be due to the time in which the study is being carried out or as a result of the methods and procedures adapted for the study.

The result on Table 3 showed a significant F-value (50.727) at 0.05 level of significance ($0.000 < 0.05$). This showed that the null hypothesis stated that principal leadership style and instructional supervision are not predictors of teachers' commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state was rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship among principal leadership style, instructional supervision and teachers' commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state, Nigeria. From the model Table, it was shown that 24.1% variability in teachers' commitment was jointly explained by leadership style and instructional supervision. This implies that instructional leadership and leadership style jointly contribute 24.1% towards teachers' commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo State, Nigeria. In furtherance, leadership style based on the coefficient result of each showed that leadership style contribution is stronger.

The result on Table 4a showed a significant t-value (5.460) and B (.254) at 0.05 level of significance ($0.000 < 0.05$). This revealed that the stated null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between principals' leadership style and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state is rejected. Thus, there is significant positive relationship between principals' leadership style and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state, Nigeria. This implies that the higher the level of principal leadership ability, the higher the level of teachers' commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state. The result of this study agrees with that of Owusu-Addo (2023) which showed that there is statistically significant relationship between leadership styles and employees' commitment. Also, the result of the study was corroborated by the study conducted by Marshall (2015) which showed a statistical significant relationship between principal leadership styles and teacher commitment.

The result on Table 4b showed a significant t-value (4.562) and B (.150) at 0.05 level of significance ($0.000 < 0.05$). This revealed that the stated null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship

between instructional supervision and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state is rejected. Thus, there is significant positive relationship between instructional supervision and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state, Nigeria. This implies that the higher the level of instructional supervision ability, the higher the level of teachers' commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state. The finding of this study is in line with the outcome of the study carried out by Sapal, Lumapenet and Salik (2023) which revealed that school heads instructional supervision significantly influences teachers' behavioural competence and commitment. The result also agrees with the outcome of the study conducted by Umaru (2018) which revealed a significant positive relationship between principal instructional supervision and teachers' job performance.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study examined principal leadership style and instructional supervision as determinants of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state. Correlational type of survey design was adopted to carry out the study. The study concluded that teachers' commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state, Nigeria was moderate and it was high in students compare to school while the commitment to profession was ranked last. The commitment of teachers can improve if there is improvement in the level principals' instructional supervision and leadership styles as there is a positive significant relationship among principal leadership style, instructional supervision and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools, Oyo state, Nigeria.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Teachers should reinforce their commitment by maintaining and sustaining their orientation that all students can succeed and it is their mission to ensure their success.
2. Principal should sustain their efforts in demanding to see assessment records of the students.
3. Principal should improve their efficacy of their instructional leadership by improving in their provision of feedback to teachers at the end of learning observation and sustain their effort in checking their teachers' scheme of work every term.
4. Principal should sustain their effort in explaining the level of performance that is expected of teachers and students, informs teachers and students about what needs to be done and how it

needs to be done, and improve in their effort on finding out what each individual teacher needs to succeed.

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